

***Chlaenius* spp. (Coleoptera:Carabidae), a leaf folder (LF) predator**

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Chlaenius ground beetles (*C. posticalis* Motschulsky, *C. nr. circumdatus*

Chaudori, and *Chlaenius* sp.) prey on LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* larvae in upland rice fields near Tanauan, Batangas, Philippines. The arboreal *Chlaenius* larvae (Fig. 1) actively search rice plants for LF larvae and were often found alone within folded leaves, presumably having consumed the LF.

In the headhouse, where predator and prey were caged at constant but variable densities, last-instar *C. posticalis* larvae exposed to 10 or more LF/cage became satiated at 1.3 last-instar LF larvae/d (Fig. 2).

LF population was highest in coconut-shaded rice fields, which in turn sustained higher carabid larval populations (see table). A more favorable prey:predator ratio occurred in sunny fields.

Chlaenius spp. did not prevent extensive leaf damage, but their activity reduced damage and population buildup. □

1. Adult and larva of *C. posticalis*, the most common species found in dryland rice fields of Batangas. The adults are ground dwellers and do not prey on LF.

2. Predation rate of *C. posticalis* larvae on LF. One carabid larva was held per cage with prey replaced daily over 1 wk, IRRRI headhouse.

Density dependent relationship of *Chlaenius* spp. ground beetle predators on host population in sunny and shaded upland rice fields^a, Tanauan, Batangas, Philippines.

Rice field	LF		Carabid predator (no. of larvae/m ²)	Prey:predator ratio
	Larvae (no./m ²)	Damaged leaves (%)		
Open	3.5 ± 2.3	65 ± 31	0.9 ± 0.9	3.9
Coconut shaded	9.8 ± 4.9	95 ± 40	1.9 ± 1.2	5.2

^a Av of 4 fields. Values are averages of 5 1-m² sample sizes (X ± SE) per field.

Rice water weevil host plants in Cuba

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Rice water weevil *Lissorhoptus brevirostris* (Suffr.) is the most-difficult-to-control rice pest in Cuba because of its habits, adult longevity of up to 714 d, and host plant range.

L. brevirostris lives in a variety of weeds on levees and in irrigation channels where weed control is difficult. If climatic conditions are unfavorable, as in Nov-Mar, the insect remains dormant on such weeds as *Brachiaria mutica*, but does not die, even without feeding for 205 d.

New records of rice water weevil host plants in Cuba, 1983.

Host plant
<i>Paspalum virgatum</i> L.
<i>Paspalum notatum</i> Fluegge
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i> Berg.
<i>Panicum maximum</i> Jacq.
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.
<i>Leptochloa filiformis</i> Lam. (Beauv.)
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.
<i>Oryza latifolia</i> Desv.
<i>Cyperus odoratus</i> L.
<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i> (Mart.) Solms

We sampled rice fields at Sur del Jibaro once a month to record *L. brevirostris* hosts. Weeds with foliage damaged by *L. brevirostris* were collected, and their roots were dissected to determine the presence of rice water weevil larvae and pupae.